

Demographic profile and satisfaction rate of patients using LNG-IUS - Mirena at tertiary care hospital of central Madhya Pradesh- An observa- tional study

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Abstract:

In this era, women's health is a very important aspect of the general health of the population. Every physician participating in the care of female patient must be familiar with the normal process of menstruation and how it may interact with other disease processes. Hence present study was undertaken to see satisfaction rate and demographic profile of all those patients visiting our hospital. A total of 50 cases were selected from a period of May 2023 to May 2024. The study was conducted at a tertiary care teaching institution and hospital. For the purpose of study, a record was maintained of - details of the patient including name, age, and Contact number, clinical data of the patient including Menstrual and obstetric history, especially parity and mode of delivery. In our study the maximum number of patients were in the perimenopausal age group of 41 to 50 years (48%). In our study, maximum number of patients with dysfunctional uterine bleeding were with previous full term vaginal deliveries (58%), followed by patients with previous caesarean section (30%). In our study, almost 64% patients were free from any medical condition. In present study after 6 months of follow up highly satisfaction was registered by 44% of patients and 34 % were satisfied with only 2% patients were dissatisfied. Thus, to conclude, Mirena is a suitable alternative before considering hysterectomy for patients with dysfunctional uterine bleeding. It has been found to have long term 5-year satisfaction rates comparable to hysterectomy and with over 90% reduction in monthly menstrual blood loss. In addition, it has advantages of long-term contraception with failure rates equaling sterilization.

Keywords: LNG- IUS, satisfaction rate, DUB.

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Introduction

In this era, women's health is a very important aspect of the general health of the population. Every physician participating in the care of female patient must be familiar with the normal process of menstruation and how it may interact with other disease processes.[1] Under normal circumstances, a woman's uterus sheds a limited amount of blood during each menstrual period. Any deviation from normal i.e., excessive bleeding in amount or duration, bleeding occurring in between menstrual periods is considered abnormal. [2]

Dysfunctional uterine bleeding is defined as abnormal uterine bleeding in the absence of organic disease. DUB is the most common cause of abnormal vaginal bleeding during a woman's reproductive years. It can cause a substantial financial and quality-of-life burden. Dysfunctional uterine bleeding is a diagnosis of exclusion.[3] Approximately

90% of these cases result from anovulation, and 10% of cases occur with ovulatory cycles. Several treatment options are available for DUB- hormone replacement therapy, D&C hysteroscopy, endometrial ablation and in severe cases hysterectomy.[4]

The most recent, safe, and effective treatment is the use of Levonorgestrel —Intrauterine System (LNG- IUS). It is a T shaped intrauterine delivery system, which after insertion releases the hormone levonorgestrel into the uterus: The vertical arm of the T-body carries a drug reservoir containing levonorgestrel.[5] LNG- IUS is used for the treatment of dysfunctional uterine bleeding, also as a contraceptive and for protection against endometrial hyperplasia during estrogen replacement therapy. It's the only IUD approved by the US FDA to treat heavy periods in women who choose an IUD for birth control. Ours is a prospective study of

assessing the satisfaction rate in LNG- US (Mirena) users during a follow up period of 6 months. [6-8]

Hence present study was undertaken to see satisfaction rate and demographic profile of all those patients visiting our hospital.

Materials and Method

A total of 50 cases were selected from a period of May 2023 to May 2024. The study was conducted at a tertiary care teaching institution and hospital. For the purpose of study, a record was maintained of details of the patient including name, age, and Contact number, clinical data of the patient including Menstrual and obstetric history, especially parity and mode of delivery.

Each patient underwent a gynecological examination including a Pap smear examination before the procedure.

All patients also had to undergo a Sonography to determine- endometrial thickness, size of the uterus and any intrauterine pathology.

Methodology used for present study: Informed written valid consent of patient and relatives was taken. A patent intravenous line was secured, and patient was asked to empty the bladder completely. Procedure was done in the operation theatre, under general anaesthesia. With patient in lithotomy position, under all aseptic precautions, parts were painted and draped. Per vaginal examination was done to assess the size, direction, mobility, surface of the uterus, the fornices and other pathology. A Sims speculum was inserted, and cervix was held with a vulsellum. Cervix was dilated using serial cervical metal dilators. Hysteroscopy was performed using STORZ 4mm rigid hysteroscope and normal saline as the distension medium to rule out any intrauterine pathology. [9]

Different levels of the uterine cavity were inspected like, endocervical canal, internal os, fundal region, anterior, posterior, and lateral walls, tubal ostia. Special mention was made regarding the endometrium. Patient was called for follow Up at later then.

Assessment was done with regard to overall improvement of Physical examination, information in Subject diary card, symptomatology.

The bleeding pattern was evaluated as

- Total number of days of bleeding (DOB)
- Total number of days of spotting (DOS)
- Total number of bleeding episodes/month (EOB)
- Total number of Spotting episodes/month (EOS)

Based on this, at the end of 6 months, the patient was asked to give a satisfaction score, i.e. the patient was asked to select a number which is considered to reflect the perceived quality of the product-Mirena.

A balanced satisfaction scale was used with the following response choices:

- 1- Very satisfied
- 2- Satisfied
- 3- Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
- 4- Dissatisfied
- 5- Very dissatisfied

Data was gathered using Microsoft excel 2021 and statistical tests were applied wherever is required using Graph pad prism 8 US for getting the results.

Results

Patients who complained of dysfunctional uterine bleeding were in the age group from 20-50 years, that is right from reproductive to menopausal age group.

In our study the maximum number of patients were in the perimenopausal age group of 41 to 50 years (48%) followed by those between 31 to 40 years (44%). The youngest patient was of 25 years and the oldest of 50 years as depicted in table 1:

Table 1: Distribution of study group as per Age Group

	Frequency	Percent
20 to 30 Yrs	4	8.00%
31 to 40 Yrs	22	44.00%
41 to 50 Yrs	24	48.00%
Total	50	100.00%

In our study, maximum number of patients were married (92%). Around 8% patients were unmarried, but sexually active, and were willing for Mirena insertion under anaesthesia, because it's

varied advantages. Distribution of study group as per marital status are Married as depicted in table 2:

Table 2: Distribution of study group as per Marital H/O

	Frequency	Percent
Married	46	92.00%
Unmarried	4	8.00%
Total	50	100.00%

Considering the distribution as per parity; in our study the incidence of dysfunctional uterine bleeding was highest in multiparous women (68%), followed by primiparous (20%). The lowest incidence

was seen in nulliparous women (12%). Mirena could be safely inserted in all women, under short general anaesthesia, whether nulliparous, primiparous, or multiparous as depicted in table 3:

Table 3: Distribution of study group as per Parity

Parity	Frequency	Percent
Nulliparous	6	12.00%
Primiparous	10	20.00%
Multiparous	34	68.00%
Total	50	100.00%

In our study, maximum number of patients with dysfunctional uterine bleeding were with previous full term vaginal deliveries (58%), followed by patients with previous caesarean section (30%). There were 7 patients with previous 2 LSCS, and 1

patient with previous 3 LSCS. Mirena insertion could be safely done, under anaesthesia, in all patients irrespective of previous mode of delivery as depicted in table 4:

Table 4: Distribution of study group as per Obstetric history

O/H	Frequency	Percent
FTND	29	58.00%
LSCS	15	30.00%
No issue	6	12%00
Total	50	100.00%

Patients with dysfunctional uterine bleeding presented with history of menorrhagia, polymenorrhagia, menometrorrhagia, irregular menses, or continuous spotting or bleeding. In the present series,

menorrhagia was found to be the commonest symptom (30%), followed by polymenorrhagia (28%) and menometrorrhagia (28%) as shown in table 5:

Table 5: Distribution of study group as per symptoms

Symptoms	Frequency	Percent
Menorrhagia	15	30.00%
Polymenorrhagia	14	28.00%
Continuous pv bleeding	3	6.00%
Irregular menses & menorrhagia	14	28.00%
Desires contraception	1	2.00%
Irregular menses	1	2.00%
Menorrhagia & intermenstrual spotting	1	2.00%
Spotting pv	1	2.00%
Total	50	100.00%

In our study, almost 64% patients were free from any medical condition, whereas, in the remaining patients, maximum number of patients were found to be suffering from Hypertension (20%), followed

by diabetes (10%). Mirena could be safely used in all patients, with these medical conditions, and no worsening of the medical condition was found even on follow up as depicted in table 6:

Table 6: Distribution of study group as per Med H/O

Med H/O	Frequency	Percent
Genital TB	1	2.00%
HTN	10	20.00%
CKD	2	4.00%
DM	5	10.00%
Hypothyroid	6	12.00%
Childhood epilepsy	1	2.00%
PCOS	2	4.00%
Rheumatoid arthritis	2	4.00%
NIL	32	64.00%

In present study after 6 months of follow up highly satisfaction was registered by 44% of patients and 34 % were satisfied with only 2% patients were

dissatisfied due to the treatment received as depicted in graph 1

Figure 1: Satisfaction of patients after 6 months

Discussion

Dysfunctional uterine bleeding is one of the commonest presenting symptoms of a women coming to the gynecology outpatient department, Dysfunctional uterine bleeding can have a substantial financial and quality-of-life burden. With the advent of LNG-IUS, patients with DUB have definitely benefited and can therefore enjoy a better quality of life. The present study evaluates the role of Mirena, with respect to its effectiveness and satisfaction rate in patients. Our study also supports the fact that Mirena is a safe and compliant treatment for DUB.

This is a prospective study of 50 patients with presenting symptoms of abnormal uterine bleeding, treated with Mirena and followed up over a period of 6 months in a tertiary care Institute.

The age of the patients in our study varied from 20 to 50 years. In our study the maximum number of patients were in the perimenopausal age group of 41 to 50 years (48%) followed by those between 31 to 40 years (44%). The youngest patient was of 25 years and the oldest of 50 years.

This is similar to a study conducted by Pace S, Villani Cet al (2001) in which they analyzed 789 patients of DUB, and they found the most common age of presentation was 41 to 50 years Our study also studies the relationship between parity and

incidence of dysfunctional uterine bleeding. In our study, the incidence of dysfunctional uterine bleeding was highest in multiparous women (68%), followed by primiparous (20%). The lowest incidence

was seen nuliparous women (12%). In our study, the most common presenting complaint of the patient was menorrhagia (30%). followed by polymenorrhagia (28%) and menometrorrhagia (28%).

A study conducted by Gimpleson R. J. Et al (1995) on 276 patients with similar complaints and found that menorrhagia was the commonest symptom in cases of DUB. [10, 11]

In our study, the improvement in symptomatology was assessed after using Mirena for 6 months. Out of 15 patients with initial complaints of menorrhagia, 14 patients (93.3%) were relieved of their symptoms. Out of 14 patients with initial complaints of polymenorrhagia, 12 patients (85.7%) were relieved of their symptoms and out of 14 patients with menometrorrhagia, 10 patients (71.4%) were relieved of their symptoms. Overall, out of 50 patients in the study, at the end of 6 months, Mirena effectively treated almost 42 patients (84%). Overall Mirena was most effective in relieving the symptom of menorrhagia, with 93.3% of patients achieving improvement of symptoms.

Andersson and Rybo in 2002 demonstrated an 86% reduction in menstrual blood loss at 3 months after placement of Mirena and a 97% reduction at 1 year after placement. [12, 13]

Tang and Lo in 2003 confirmed the efficacy of Mirena in the treatment of menorrhagia without organic cause. Menstrual blood loss was reduced by 54%, 87% and 95% after 1,3 and 6 months of treatment, respectively, compared with pre-treatment cycles. After 6 months, the total number

of bleeding days had been reduced by a median of 6 days, and menstrual cycle length increased by a median of 12 days in 9 months. [14, 15]

Andrew Kaunitz MD, Florida (May 2008) undertook a study and concluded that treatment with LNG-IUS produced statistically significant greater reduction in blood loss. The preparation of subjects with improvement with LNG-IUS at 8 months was 13.6%. [16]

In our study, the satisfaction rates of Mirena users at the end of 6 months was analysed. Out of 50 patients, 17 (34%) patients were very satisfied with the use of LNG-IUS, followed by 22 patients (44%) who were also satisfied. 8 patients (16%) were neither satisfied nor dissatisfied with the use of LNG-IUS. 2% of the patients were dissatisfied, and 4% of the patients were very dissatisfied with the use of Mirena Overall the satisfaction rate in Mirena users was about 78%.

This is similar to a study by undertaken by Radesic B and Sharma A from June 1998 to June 2002 in the Women's Health Department, Palmerston North Hospital, New Zealand. Their aim was to establish satisfaction and continuation rates of LNG-IUS, in 120 women using LNG-IUS over 6 months. The results obtained were an overall continuation rate of 87% and satisfaction rate of 90%. The study thus concluded LNG-IUS as a well-accepted and effective therapy for DUB. [17]

T. Nagaish, F. Rizvi, A.Khan, M. Afzal et al from Islamabad, Pakistan undertook a prospective study from Sept 2011 to Sept 2012. 119 patients in the age group of 28 to 60 years with DUB were selected and a patient satisfaction questionnaire was used at the end of 6 months. The results showed that the satisfaction level was significantly greater with LNG-IUS as compared to norethisterone. (90% vs. 20%) $p < 0.05$. The preference of continuing the method as well as recommendation to others was significantly greater with LNG-IUS than with norethisterone. The study thus concluded that LNG-IUS is better choice as compared to norethisterone for treatment of DUB with 90% patients highly satisfied. [18]

Conclusion

Thus, to conclude, Mirena is a suitable alternative before considering hysterectomy for patients with dysfunctional uterine bleeding. It has been found to have long term 5-year satisfaction rates comparable to hysterectomy and with over 90% reduction in monthly menstrual blood loss. In addition, it has advantages of long-term contraception with failure rates equaling sterilization. There is recent evidence that even in women with fibroids. Mirena helps reduce the monthly blood loss. It combines the best features of hormonal contraceptives and IUDs and adds a few advantages of its own.

Though costly by its own, Mirena in the long run, proves to be a cost-effective alternative in the treatment of DUB, as compared to prolonged use of progesterone, oral or injectable, or OCPs. Now-a-days, with more and more women, who refuse to take the drastic plunge to hysterectomy, Mirena has proved to be the knight in shining armor.

Thus, Mirena is the ne new age, safe, effective, and dysfunctional uterine bleeding, a non-invasive modality for the treatment of DUB.

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